

SPG Mitteilungen Communications de la SSP

Auszug - Extrait

The Nobel Prizes in Physics and Chemistry 2024

This article has been downloaded from:
https://www.sps.ch/articles/nobel_prizes/

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15213099](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15213099)

The Nobel Prizes in Physics and Chemistry 2024

It is customary for our editorial team to react on the awarding of the Nobel Prizes in Physics in the fall issue of the *SPG Mitteilungen*. However, in view of the short period of time between the official announcement and the editorial deadline, we can only essentially repeat what the Nobel Committee officially published. But this leaves enough time until the spring issue to go into more detail about the laureates in physics and, when appropriate, in chemistry, and to describe their honored achievements. Nevertheless, it is always difficult to find competent colleagues who are willing to make this effort and who ideally are even in personal contact with the laureates.

So we are happy to present two interesting articles below. In the first one, Tobi Delbrück (UZH - ETH Zürich) describes one of the two physics prize winners, **John Hopfield**, with whom he spent his PhD years at Caltech in the USA. We apologize that we cannot

also comment in depth on the second laureate **Geoff Hinton**. For the second article, SPS board member Christof Fattinger succeeded in inviting two chemists to share their views on the 2024 Nobel Prize in Chemistry. See his introduction and their assessment below.

The fascinating thematic complementarity and mutual supplementation of both articles is enriched by a historic coincidence: Tobi Delbrück is the son of Max Ludwig Henning Delbrück (1906 - 1981), a German-American biophysicist who stimulated physical scientists' interest into biology, especially as to basic research to physically explain genes, mysterious at the time. Max Delbrück was honored with the Nobel Prize for Physiology and Medicine in 1969.

Bernhard Braunecker

What does the 2024 Nobel Prize in Chemistry, awarded to David Baker, Demis Hassabis and John Jumper, mean for the life sciences and biomedical research?

Two answer this scientific question, two reputable chemists, one from academia and one from industry, were invited by the Swiss Physical Society to contribute an article about last year's Nobel Prize in Chemistry to this issue of the *SPG Mitteilungen*. This article by Johan Åqvist and Hubert Kettenberger highlights the scientific interaction between academic and industrial research.

It is the cross-fertilization of scientific insight and technological needs where ingenuity and inventiveness in commercial research can lead to profound breakthrough discoveries [1]. Nobel prizes for

applied research provide recognition for innovations with profound impact, fully in tune with the intentions of Alfred Nobel [1].

A beautiful summary of the achievements honoured through the Nobel prize, whether applied or fundamental in nature, is the Latin inscription on the Nobel prize medals for physics and chemistry. It is taken from Virgil's Aeneid, sixth verse, line 663: *Inventas vitam juvat excoluisse per artes*, which loosely translates as: "And they who bettered life on earth by their newly found mastery." [1]

Christof Fattinger, SPS Section Biophysics and Soft Matter

[1] Editorial: Applied research deserves Nobel prizes, *Nature Materials*, Vol 9, January 2010. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmat2602>

How John Hopfield energized neural computation at Caltech

Tobi Delbrück, Sensors Group, Inst. of Neuroinformatics (INI), UZH-ETH Zurich, <https://www.ini.uzh.ch/>

A month ago I woke with joy to see the news that **John Hopfield** and **Geoff Hinton** had been awarded the **2024 Nobel prize in physics**. What followed this announcement is interesting. There were comments on social media such as "Hinton ok... But Hopfield??" and "I mean they might as well have gone back to the perceptron". (See my slides¹ presented at our lab meeting for more comments). These callow comments came from researchers who didn't live through this early period and who are unaware of recent developments. Thus I'm extremely grateful to have the opportunity from the SPS to write this personal account of the Hopfield effect on me and I believe others at Caltech. I was the first student in the Caltech Computation and Neural Systems program formed by Hopfield and owe my career to the foundation of experience from my Caltech mentors.

I advise anyone reading this account to stop here and simply read Hopfield's mesmerizing and multifaceted account of the formation of Caltech's Computation and Neural Sys-

tems study program², never published but valuable for anyone thinking of establishing a research program. Here I only quote the closing lines:

"Moving the intellectual focus of a university is somewhat like moving a graveyard. In both cases you should expect little help from the inhabitants."

At the start of the 1980s, practical methods of machine learning consisted mainly of clustering methods and single layer perceptrons [1], famously proven incapable of doing even the trivial XOR problem [2]. I recall doing an exercise in Pietro Perona's course to train a single layer perceptron to separate two classes of points on a plane, by finding a line between them. It was not at all interesting, simply an exercise in fitting data. Computer vision and time-domain signal processing were based on beautiful, highly evolved, but ultimately limited hand-crafted algorithms. Support vector machines, kernel methods, restricted Boltzmann machines,

¹ https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1qkE7c866QuZc7gq8n5h24uFrsAs99g9NC-6C_atwt-s/edit?usp=sharing

² https://drive.google.com/file/d/0BzvXOhBHjRheRWxBM0xDOU45a2M/view?usp=sharing&resourcekey=0-xNtGQt1YJjL9_uWNbodag

Hopfield giving a talk at the kickoff of the Inst. of Neuroinformatics, 1996. Credit: Kevan Martin.

deep networks, CNNs, RNNs, transformers, large language models, and all that stuff were still decades in the future and had to wait for the internet data deluge, gamer enthusiasm for better GPUs, and general silicon scaling. There was hardly any connection between neuroscience and AI, and the Caltech neuroscientists (according to Hopfield's memo to Caltech) were opposed to a broader approach less focused on details of the systems they studied. Yes, there were lovely methods like Kohonen's self-organizing feature maps [3] (of which I recall hearing beautiful synthetic organ pieces playing at an early neural network meeting). Amari had published some lovely work on memory formation and dynamical patterns arising from feedback; he even formulated Hopfield's network in 1972 [4], albeit less transparently. There were also theories like "adaptive resonance" [5] but they seemed to us (or at least me) to be laden with terminology, without practical utility and buried in long papers that were very hard to read.

In 1980, Hopfield, by then an established expert in theoretical solid state physics, moved to Caltech. What followed is best read in Hopfield's account cited above. I will focus on the effect of his PNAS papers and Caltech teaching on me and my fellow CNS students and conclude with a brief account of recent developments.

In 1982, two years after his move and memo to Caltech, Hopfield published his first PNAS paper on neural networks [6]. It was only 5 pages and 2 figures and it described a way to formulate a fully-connected binary stochastic recurrent network with symmetric weights as a very simple 1-line energy function. The memories were the minimas of this energy function. You could store memories in this network just by adding to the connection weights the outer product of the memory with itself, and recall memories by feeding in part of them on the input vector and then letting the network relax

to a stable point. And he proved in about 2 lines of math that it was guaranteed to be stable, i. e. given some corrupted memory input to drive the population vector toward a particular direction, it would ultimately settle into a stable state at a corner of the hypercube. Two years later the second 5-page PNAS paper [7] generalized this stochastic binary network to analog neuron values and proposed a simple electronic implementation that was shown in one figure, reproduced below.

FIG. 2. An electrical circuit that corresponds to Eq. 5 when the amplifiers are fast. The input capacitance and resistances are not drawn. A particularly simple special case can have all positive T_{ij} of the same strength and no negative T_{ij} and replaces the array of negative wires with a single negative feedback amplifier sending a common output to each "neuron."

From 1984 PNAS paper

I cannot overemphasize the effect of these two papers (at least on the Caltech community of which I was a part). They were short and written so clearly that most of the paper could be understood on first reading. They made it clear that it was possible to formulate a kind of collective recurrent computation with a physics-inspired energy scheme. It did not matter that these networks solved no real problems. It did not matter that in subsequent years there appeared a mole of rather boring papers computing the memory capacity of these networks. Hopfield's papers, together with the new CNS program and its courses that were taught by Hopfield, Mead, and the biologists van Essen, Allman, Konishi, and others galvanized the Caltech students in the same way that Hopfield had been galvanized: To consider the study of natural and artificial intelligence as open frontiers of research, in a way that could somewhat disconnect them from their detailed biochemistry or electronic implementation.

I have a clear memory of how, in his 1983 Caltech CNS class lecture about language, Hopfield wrote this on the blackboard:

"Time flies like an arrow"

He let that sink it for a moment. It makes sense, right?

Then, he wrote this:

"Fruit flies like a banana"

Huh? It takes a moment to realize you need to switch your context about the word "flies" where you see a banana flying

through the air to understand it means drosophila like to eat fruit. So language processing requires context, stored in a memory, and this memory takes time to flush and reload. It was examples like this that Hopfield used to stimulate thinking about the nature of brain computation.

My own work as a student with Carver Mead partly turned to implementing this vision of collective computation, in a series of David Marr-inspired [8] stereo vision matching chips I built with Misha Mahowald, for whom we named the *Mahowald Prizes in Neuromorphic Engineering*³. And I stopped following the increasingly complex world of algorithmic artificial neural networks or the literature from Hopfield, since it was not related to my work on silicon retina chips. Hopfield did not take on a role like Hinton in the explosive development of contemporary AI, probably from a combination of his big distaste for fundraising and because Caltech missed the chance to establish a center like MILA in Montreal. But he has continued, up to 2020, most notably with his collaborator Dimitri Krotov, to publish⁴ papers nearly every year about the nature of dynamical computation in the nervous system – for example in odor sniffing [9] and on methods to learn early features using local learning rules [10]. These efforts were countercultural, because by the middle 1990s, deep learning was entering its long myopic focus on supervised learning, by curve fitting with gradient descent in the weight space as a brute-force solution to training practical networks. Only very recently have the early Hopfield ideas about formulating memory as energy minimization had mainstream AI impact.

It's interesting to see the recent developments that have brought the original network in sharp and topical focus for practical large-scale AI [11]. Not too long ago, Krotov and Hopfield proposed the “dense associative memory” [12], aka the *modern Hopfield network*⁵. It solves the problem that the original network actually had extremely limited memory capacity of only about 15 % of its vector length in patterns. For a 100-unit net with 10k weights, the original net could only store about 15 uncorrelated patterns. This capacity is really pitiful. It is a miniscule fraction of the possible states and number of weights. The modern version cleverly solves this problem by realizing that the many local minima are analogous to local spin glass states, and massively increases the memory capacity by introducing a steeper activation function as the state approaches a memory. [13] gives a wonderful physics perspective of the impact of these recent developments on really large AI networks like language models, where transformer blocks are shown to be Hopfield networks that use a soft winner-take-all activation function that implicitly compares the neuron outputs with each other.

If it were not for Hopfield, my own field of neuromorphic engineering would not exist in its current form, and the course of AI would be significantly different. And if there are simple lessons to be gained, they might be that the impact of a paper can be correlated with its clarity and brevity and that establishing a field requires deep curiosity and a tenacious pa-

tience with politics and bureaucracy, which are well-known to be creatures that are first and foremost organisms that feeds themselves.

Shih-Chii Liu discussing work with Hopfield at INI March 15, 2002. On the right, Patrick Lichtsteiner (then masters student). credit: T. Delbrück.

References

- [1] F. Rosenblatt, “The Perceptron: A Probabilistic Model for Information Storage and Organization in the Brain.” *Psychological Review* **65** (6): 386–408 (1958). <https://paperpile.com/b/Wsh4j/yeUp>
- [2] M. L. Minsky and S. A. Papert, *Perceptrons*, Cambridge: MIT Press (1969). <https://paperpile.com/b/Wsh4j/JOOl>
- [3] T. Kohonen, *Self-Organization and Associative Memory*. Berlin: Springer (1984). <https://paperpile.com/b/Wsh4j/dKrr>
- [4] S. Amari, “Learning Patterns and Pattern Sequences by Self-Organizing Nets of Threshold Elements.” *IEEE Transactions on Computers. Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers C-21* (November): 1197–1206 (1972). <https://doi.org/10.1109/T-C.1972.223477>.
- [5] G. Carpenter and S. Grossberg, *Pattern Recognition by Self-Organizing Neural Networks*. MIT Press (1991). <https://paperpile.com/b/Wsh4j/ZeR9>
- [6] J. Hopfield, “Neural Networks and Physical Systems with Emergent Collective Computational Abilities.” *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* **79** (8): 2554–58 (1982). <https://paperpile.com/b/Wsh4j/1vRv>
- [7] J. Hopfield, “Neurons with Graded Response Have Collective Computational Properties like Those of Two-State Neurons.” *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* **81** (10): 3088–92 (1984). <https://doi.org/10.1073/PNAS.81.10.3088>, <https://paperpile.com/c/Wsh4j/tuMd>
- [8] D. Marr, T. A. Poggio, and S. Ullman. *Vision: A Computational Investigation into the Human Representation and Processing of Visual Information*. The MIT Press (2010). https://www.amazon.com/Vision-Computational-Investigation-Representation-Information/dp/0262514621/ref=sr_1_1?d-child=1&keywords=david+marr+vision&qid=1596898262&sr=8-1, <https://paperpile.com/c/Wsh4j/pin0>
- [9] J. J. Hopfield and C. D. Brody, “Learning Rules and Network Repair in Spike-Timing-Based Computation Networks.” *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* **101** (1): 337–42 (2004). <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2536316100>, <https://paperpile.com/b/Wsh4j/8ZV0>
- [10] D. Krotov and J. J. Hopfield, “Unsupervised Learning by Competing Hidden Units.” *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* **116** (16): 7723–31 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1820458116>, <https://paperpile.com/b/Wsh4j/9wje>
- [11] “Hopfield Networks Is All You Need.” Hopfield-Layers. August 25, 2020. <https://ml-jku.github.io/hopfield-layers/>, <https://paperpile.com/b/Wsh4j/Fsvx>
- [12] D. Krotov and J. Hopfield. “Dense Associative Memory for Pattern Recognition.” *Neural Information Processing Systems abs/1606.01164* (June 2016). https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=en&citation_for_view=SNhXppAAAAAJ:hC7cP41nSMkC, <https://paperpile.com/c/Wsh4j/OV6s>
- [13] D. Krotov, “A New Frontier for Hopfield Networks.” *Nature Reviews. Physics* **5** (May): 366–67 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42254-023-00595-y>, <https://paperpile.com/c/Wsh4j/j7jN>

³ <https://mahowaldprize.org/>

⁴ https://scholar.google.ch/citations?hl=en&user=SNhXppAAAAAJ&view_op=list_works&sortBy=pubdate

⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Modern_Hopfield_network#cite_note-3-1

Computational Protein Design and Protein Structure Prediction

Johan Åqvist, Cell & Molecular Biology, Uppsala University, Member of the Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences
 Hubert Kettenberger, Head of Computational Protein Engineering, Roche Pharma Research and Early Development (pRED), Roche Diagnostics GmbH, Penzberg

The 2024 Nobel Prize in Chemistry is about proteins, life's ingenious chemical tools. It has been awarded with one half to **David Baker** (University of Washington, USA) "for computational protein design" and the other half jointly to **Demis Hassabis** and **John M. Jumper** (both affiliated with Google DeepMind, London, UK) "for protein structure prediction". Both discoveries open up vast possibilities with enormous potential.

What does the 2024 Nobel Prize in Chemistry mean for the life sciences and biomedical research?

Abstract

The advancements in computational protein design and protein structure prediction, which were recognised with the 2024 Nobel Prize for chemistry, have ushered in a transformative period in life sciences with profound implications for medical research and drug development. The introduction of computational tools such as AlphaFold has enabled the generation of highly precise models of proteins and other biomolecules, crucial for understanding cellular functions and interactions. Breakthroughs in protein design hold the promise for making the drug discovery and development processes more efficient and effective, reducing the time and cost associated with bringing new drugs to the market. The creation of completely novel protein structures through computational design further expands the potential for therapeutic innovation, allowing the development of bespoke proteins with tailored functions. Swiss research institutions and pharmaceutical companies are actively involved in harnessing and advancing these exciting new developments.

Introduction

What have silk, hair, muscles, enzymes and a gummy bear in common? They are all made (essentially) of proteins. Proteins are a universal building material of central components of living organisms. Chemically, proteins are polymers in which 20 different "canonical" amino acids, precisely arranged in "sequences" like beads on a string form a long

chain. The exact sequence and the chain's specific three-dimensional structure determine the functional, mechanical and chemical properties of proteins, such as their enzymatic activity, molecular recognition and binding affinity. Consequently, the understanding of the relationship between protein sequence and 3D structure is a crucial prerequisite to understanding and controlling protein functions at the molecular level.

In 1972, Christian Anfinsen was awarded the Nobel Prize in Chemistry for the remarkable finding that protein 3D structures were basically encoded by the sequence of amino acids in the polypeptide chain [1]. This finding led to the long scientific quest of predicting 3D structures directly from the amino acid sequence. The problem is considered so important that Nobel Prize Laureate Venki Ramakrishnan has described it as a "50-year-old grand challenge in biology" [2].

Despite progress in automation and data processing, determining protein structures by experimental means is labour intensive. It is noteworthy that while the number of DNA sequences in public databases is now close to 3 billion, and the number of protein sequences that have so far been identified in organisms is over 200 million, the Protein Data Bank [3] still contains only a small fraction of experimen-

Figure 1. Hierarchy of protein structure. (A) Primary structure, i.e., the sequence of amino acids as encoded by the protein-coding DNA. (B) Secondary structure, formation of regular geometric patterns of α -helices and β -sheets. (C) Tertiary structure, the detailed 3D shape of the polypeptide chain. (D) Quaternary structure, the association of several polypeptide chains or subunits. The protein depicted is human haemoglobin (PDB 1shr).

tal 3D protein structures (~ 200 000). To be able to reliably predict protein structures directly from the amino acid sequence would thus be a major achievement.

The structure prediction problem can be formulated in another way, where one instead asks what amino acid sequences would yield a certain folding pattern. This question is at the heart of protein design, a field where a target structure is envisaged and then sequences that would yield this structure are identified by computational means.

This year's Nobel Prize in Chemistry recognizes decisive breakthroughs in solving both of these problems – structure prediction from sequence and sequence prediction from structure – and the implications are truly profound. Most monomeric protein structures can now be predicted with high fidelity, and large databases of hundreds of millions of predicted structures have thus been created. Likewise, completely new protein structures, not found in nature, can now be created by computational design and used in various biotechnological and biomedical applications.

Background

After determination of the first protein structures [4,5], it was immediately recognized that tertiary (3D) structures of proteins contain recurring so-called secondary structure elements, such as α -helices and β -sheets, the orientation and packing of which, together with connecting loop regions, define the actual tertiary topology (Figure 1). In fact, the α -helical polypeptide pattern was predicted by Linus Pauling as early as 1951 [6]. The earliest attempts to predict protein structure from amino acid sequence therefore focused on secondary structure prediction, rather than tertiary.

The first steps towards protein design were taken in the late 1980s, focusing on alpha helix bundles which follow rather simple biophysical principles. These simple biophysical principles did not suffice for construction of more complex structures, such as mixed α/β -topologies, or to predict the structures at atomic detail. The breadth of the problem clearly called for an automated computational approach.

Computational protein design

The first successful design of a small protein via computation was published by Dahiyat and Mayo in 1997 [7]. As a target, they chose the so-called zinc-finger motif that coordinates one or two Zn^{2+} ions. This structure is largely stabilized by interactions with the Zn^{2+} ions, and the goal of the design was to find a new sequence that would adopt the same structure but without any metal ions. The generation of new proteins with sequences unrelated to those in nature is usually termed *de novo* protein design.

The Zn-finger structure is relatively small, made up of ~ 30 amino acids, and contains one α -helical segment and two β -strands, plus connecting short loops ($\beta\beta\alpha$ motif). Dahiyat and Mayo [7] kept the natural polypeptide backbone fixed, removed the Zn^{2+} ions and computationally searched for amino acid sequences that would yield the desired 3D structure. The resulting design had 6 out of 28 residues in common with the original Zn-finger sequence and its 3D structure was determined by NMR spectroscopy, demon-

Figure 2. A) Experimental (NMR) structure of the designed zinc-finger protein by Dahiyat and Mayo [7] (PDB 1fsd) compared with (B) the naturally occurring zinc finger motif of ZIF268 that served as a design target (PDB 1a1l) [7].

strating a close resemblance to the computationally predicted structure (Figure 2).

This study represents an important milestone in protein design but the approach was limited to relatively short sequences and did not allow for deviation of a given protein backbone conformation [8].

The breakthrough in computational *de novo* protein design came in 2003, when **David Baker** and coworkers published the design and crystallographic validation of a 93-residue α/β -protein named Top7 [9]. This was a remarkable achievement for several reasons. First, it was a relatively large protein with two α -helices and a β -sheet made up from five β -strands (Figure 3), and its predicted structure was in agreement with the experimental one, including the detailed sidechain positions. Second, the authors sought to design a folding pattern not found for any globular protein in the Protein Data Bank. And third, the final Top7 design had no significant sequence similarity to any naturally occurring protein in the sequence databases. Hence, Top7 was an entirely new protein, both structurally and sequence-wise, designed by automated computation with full optimization of both backbone and sidechains.

Figure 3. Xray structure of the computationally designed TOP7 protein (PDB 1qys) [9]. Alpha helices are shown in red, loops shown in green and beta sheets in yellow [9].

How did Baker and his coworkers solve the problem? The key to success here was their initial development a few years earlier (1999) of the Rosetta suite of computational tools [10]. The underlying algorithm assembles short structural fragments from unrelated protein structures [11] with similar local sequences in the Protein Data Bank, and these structures are then simultaneously optimized for their sequence and structural similarity with respect to the backbone conformation of the target protein. Their program thereby generates several putative solutions, which are ranked by their predicted stabilities.

Most importantly, Rosetta was designed to be a general program both for protein structure prediction and design, and since its inception, it was continuously developed further with a large cadre of users and co-developers [12]. While protein design was initially just focused on designing structures, more recent work has aimed to also design advanced protein functions. This still poses major challenges in terms of understanding protein dynamics, structural transitions, allostery, catalytic effects, and so forth, and is thus an area of active research.

In 2008, Baker and coworkers reported the first attempts at *de novo* enzyme design, or the design of enzymes that can catalyse reactions for which no naturally occurring enzymes exist [13,14]. Those first *de novo* designed enzymes showed some activity but their overall rates were relatively low compared to those of natural enzymes and could later be improved by rounds of experimental directed evolution (for which Frances Arnold was awarded the Nobel Prize in Chemistry 2018).

In the area of ligand-binding proteins, Baker and coworkers could design protein structures that bind for example steroids with high affinity and selectivity. Again, a combination of *in-silico* design followed by laboratory evolution was used to reach high affinities [15]. This work paved the way to other classes of designed proteins such as self-assembling virus-like particles [16], protein switches and sensors for different analytes [17,18].

Protein structure prediction from sequence – breakthrough by deep learning

In nature, proteins typically adopt their 3D structure co-translationally, i.e., in the moment they are made by ribosomes, sometimes with the help of folding-assisting cofactors, so-called chaperones. For decades, researchers tried to reproduce this process *in-silico* and predict the 3D structure of folded proteins from their sequence. Progress in the field has been slow for decades as shown in biannual so-called CASP experiments (Critical Assessment of protein Structure Prediction) founded by John Moult and Krzysztof Fidelis in 1994 [19].

Figure 4. Left: progress of the CASP performance over the years for the best models and the most difficult targets [23] Right: performance of AlphaFold2 relative to the top 15 entries by other groups in CASP14. Data are the median coordinate error and the 95 % confidence interval of the median, estimated from 10 000 bootstrap samples [24].

The accuracy of 3D structure predictions in CASP is measured in terms of a global distance test (GDT) score that reports the largest percentage of α -carbons falling within a certain distance cutoff from the experimental structure, after iteratively superimposing the two structures [20]. Despite the progress outlined above, the average GDT score for the best *ab initio* predictions was stuck below 40 % up until and including CASP12 in 2016 (Figure 4).

A sudden accuracy leap by neural networks

The CASP13 contest in 2018 witnessed a sudden major improvement. The main reason for this improvement was the impact of deep learning methods using convolutional neural networks and the successful learning of evolutionary patterns in proteins through large multiple-sequence alignments (MSAs) of related proteins.

For the CASP13 experiment in 2018, the company DeepMind, founded and led by **Demis Hassabis**, constructed a computer program based on a convolutional neural network, which they called AlphaFold (now known as AlphaFold1 or AF1) [21]. The program was trained on experimental structures and multiple sequence alignments to produce a distance map between residues, or rather a map of probability distributions for the distances. From this map, the complete 3D structure of a protein can be generated [21].

With deep learning entering the structure prediction field, the performance had now risen to a GDT score of about 60 % (Figure 4), and the AlphaFold team was clearly ahead of other participants. Hassabis and his team had already taken the community of Go and Chess players by storm in 2018, when they published the AlphaZero program, also based on deep learning, that showed unsurpassed performance in these and other two-party games [22]. However, there was still some way to go for protein structure prediction to reach near-experimental accuracy.

AlphaFold2 – the real breakthrough

In the 2020 round of CASP (CASP14), the group from DeepMind had again achieved another leap in accuracy which was competitive with experimental structures for a multitude of targets. The GDT score for the best predictions on difficult

Figure 5. Schematic description of the two main modules of AF2. An input sequence together with data from sequence and structure databases serve as input to the Evoformer. The Structure module produces as output a 3D model of the protein structure corresponding to the input sequence.

targets [25] had now reached about 90 % using the new AlphaFold2 (AF2) algorithm [24] (Figure 4). A GDT score of about 90 % is generally considered on par with experimental accuracy, since experimental structure determination is, of course, also associated with some errors. The AF2 team led by **John Jumper** and Demis Hassabis had thus finally succeeded in solving the protein structure prediction problem for monomeric proteins to within a backbone accuracy of about 1 Å.

The convolution approach used in AF1 was abandoned in AF2, and instead a transformer architecture was used, with the essential attention mechanism for learning which parts of the input are more important for the objective of network [26].

The AF2 network has two main blocks called the Evoformer and the Structure module (Figure 5). The Evoformer works simultaneously with a multiple sequence alignment representation (a 2D matrix of aligned sequences from different species) and a pair representation (a 2D matrix of pair distances). The multiple sequence alignment and pair representations exchange information during the learning process and update each other, thus allowing both to evolve. The Structure module converts the distance map to a 3D structure and the resulting structure model is then recycled back to the Evoformer a number of times to improve the final result [24].

Overall, the AF2 architecture can be described as an ingenious piece of neural network engineering by Jumper, Hassabis and their coworkers, with a multitude of new inventions. The fact that the AF2 source code was made public also decisively contributed to its impact, as it could be extensively tested, validated and expanded to new problems such as predicting protein complexes. A deep learning architecture similar to that of AF2 was also rapidly adopted by Baker and colleagues in the program RoseTTAfold [27].

The transformative successes of AF2 and RoseTTAfold sparked the development of numerous tools which expanded their applicability to e.g. multimeric proteins, molecule dynamics or protein conformations and made these tools

easily accessible to researchers [28–32].

AlphaFold3: Expanding modelling capabilities beyond proteins

AlphaFold3 (AF3), presented by Abramson et al. in May 2024 and developed by IsomorphicLabs (London, UK and Lausanne, CH) and DeepMind [33] represents a significant leap forward in the field of computational protein design, employing an innovative diffusion-based architecture that parallels those used in state-of-the-art AI image generation models. This novel architecture allows AF3 to model complex biomolecular structures by iteratively diffusing input features into high-confidence predictions. The inspiration from AI image generators lies in their

ability to construct detailed, high-resolution images from noisy inputs, which AF3 adapts to predict intricate biomolecular configurations with remarkable detail.

AF3 overcomes the limitations of previous versions to model other important biomolecules (glycans, nucleic acids) and protein interactions with small molecule ligands and ions, which are fundamental to numerous biological processes. This capability is vital for understanding molecular mechanisms in greater detail and facilitates the comprehensive simulation of cellular environments that include diverse types of biomolecular interactions.

AF3 can produce highly precise models of multi-protein assemblies, which are critical for elucidating the mechanisms of cellular functions and interactions. The enhanced prediction capabilities make AF3 an indispensable tool for researchers studying the structural basis of protein function and interactions, significantly advancing the field of structural biology.

The advancements made by AlphaFold3 are particularly consequential for medical research and drug design [34]. Many pathological conditions and disease states are deeply rooted in aberrant protein interactions and complex biomolecular processes. By accurately modelling these interactions, AF3 provides invaluable insights that can potentially lead to the identification of potential drug targets and the design of novel therapeutic agents. Furthermore, AF3's capabilities can be instrumental in identifying biomarkers for diseases and understanding resistance mechanisms, paving the way for personalized medicine and more effective treatments.

Unlike AF2, AF3 is not available for commercial use but Isomorphic Labs signed partnerships with several pharmaceutical companies to harness AF3's capabilities for drug research [34,35]. Using similar deep learning methodologies, however, several groups are now proposing AF3 alternatives such as BOLTZ-136 and CHAI-1 [35].

Contributions of Swiss research institutions

Protein structure prediction and design methods which rely on deep learning, require large corpora of experimental training data, the vast majority of them being the result of x-ray crystallography at synchrotron beamlines (followed by cryo electron microscopy which saw strong technological advancements in the recent years). Remarkably, more than one in 20 (5.5 % according to <https://www.rcsb.org/stats>) x-ray structures were obtained at the Swiss Light Source (SLS) at the Paul Scherrer Institute in Villigen. The SLS has thus contributed a significant share of the experimental data basis leading to this year's Nobel Prizes. The planned upgrade to SLS 2.0, planned to become operational in 2026, will guarantee sustained Swiss presence in this research area [37].

Structure prediction and design of antibodies: A different challenge

The structure prediction and design of antibodies are critical areas of research, given that antibodies represent the most widely used class of protein therapeutics. The precision with which antibodies recognize their specific antigens is essential for their efficacy, and this specificity and affinity are central to the development of new therapeutic antibodies. Structure prediction and design approaches like AlphaFold, which are based on multiple sequence alignment (MSA)-based distance prediction, are inadequate for antibodies due to their unique evolutionary path and the largely unknown evolutionary history within the evolving B-cell immune repertoire. To address this gap, specialized tools such as IgFold [38], ImmuneBuilder [39], Equifold [40] and DeepAB [41] have been developed, leveraging neural network methodologies inspired by the pioneering work by Jumper, Hassabis and Baker, to predict antibody structures.

What does this mean for biomedical research and protein-based drug discovery?

With the recent advances in protein structure prediction, it is now straightforward to predict the structures of disease-relevant proteins and protein complexes. Using the lock-and-key analogy, where a therapeutic drug represents the key which specifically and tightly matches its target, it is now possible to predict the structure of the "lock", i.e., the drug target. This is particularly relevant in cases where no experimental structure is available, e.g., for very understudied targets or for difficult-to-handle proteins such as multi-pass transmembrane proteins. Knowing the target structure is a first step in the long process of designing new drugs. *In-silico* biotherapeutics discovery takes a target structure as its input and tries to predict proteins which confer their mode of action by tightly binding to a desired landing site on the target. Target binding is a necessary but by no means sufficient prerequisite for an effective drug. Features like similarity to human proteins (to avoid unwanted immunogenicity reactions), specificity, chemical and physical stability, solubility, manufacturability etc. need to be considered. The most widely used class of protein-based therapeutics are monoclonal antibodies whose structures and interactions with target proteins are, as described above, intrinsically difficult to predict with any current method due to their inherent flexibility and lack of evolutionary information. Despite the

recent advancements, predicting the structure of antibodies bound to their antigens from sequence alone remains surprisingly challenging. The same is true for the *de novo* design of antibodies, i.e., predicting antibody sequences which bind to a given target antigen, where outcomes are still anecdotal for actual antibodies, while smaller single-domain VHH antibodies typically yield better results. In any case, the current state-of-the-art approach involves the *in-silico* generation of target-conditioned antibody libraries (i.e. hundreds or thousands of antibody sequences), from which specific antibodies are then isolated [42]. Those "hits" then need to be extensively tested and validated *in-vitro* and *in-vivo*.

The first non-antibody-based computer-designed biotherapeutic, NL-201, developed by Neoleukin Inc., started a Phase I clinical trial in 2021. NL-201 was designed to treat cancer by combining the mode of action of two different natural immune stimulators. It was, however, later discontinued due to a lack of differentiation from (natural) interleukin drugs¹. Notwithstanding, a large number of drug developers are working on advancing computer-generated biotherapeutics to clinical trials [43] for several reasons: Bypassing the need for experimental binder generation would allow a scalable approach to new biotherapeutics, in particular against targets which are difficult to handle experimentally. Moreover, designed proteins may be endowed with special features like ultra-high stability or conditional activation, which are not easily found in nature [17]. Lastly, alternative protein formats beyond antibodies, which might be more amenable to computational design, are seeing increasing research interest [44,45].

Summary and outlook

The achievements of **David Baker**, **Demis Hassabis** and **John Jumper** in the fields of computational protein design and protein structure prediction are truly profound. Their work has opened up a new era of biochemical and biological research, where we can now predict and design protein structures in ways that had not been possible before. Hence, a long-standing goal has been achieved, and the impact of this will have far-reaching consequences. With many of these algorithms being freely available and a database of predicted (> 200 million) protein structures being shared in a public database [46], the scientific community has immediately started to build on this work: Countless publications in the area of structural biology, biomedical research, bioinformatics and biophysics that are based on this pioneering work have emerged in the recent months. The era of AI applied in protein structure prediction and protein design has just begun and promises far-reaching implications in the field of life sciences, drug research and synthetic biology.

References

- [1] Anfinsen, C. B., Principles that Govern the Folding of Protein Chains. *Science* **181**, 223–230 (1973).
- [2] Bouatta, N., Sorger, P. & Al Quraishi, M., Protein structure prediction by AlphaFold2: are attention and symmetries all you need? *Acta Crystallogr. Sect. D, Struct. Biol.* **77**, 982–991 (2021).

¹ <https://www.biospace.com/neoleukin-therapeutics-slashes-workforce-drops-de-novo-protein-therapeutic>

- [3] Bernstein, F. C. *et al.*, The protein data bank: A computer-based archival file for macromolecular structures. *Arch. Biochem. Biophys.* **185**, 584–591 (1978).
- [4] Kendrew, J. C. *et al.*, A Three-Dimensional Model of the Myoglobin Molecule Obtained by X-Ray Analysis. *Nature* **181**, 662–666 (1958).
- [5] Perutz, M. F. *et al.*, Structure of Hæmoglobin: A Three-Dimensional Fourier Synthesis at 5.5-Å. Resolution, Obtained by X-Ray Analysis. *Nature* **185**, 416–422 (1960).
- [6] Pauling, L., Corey, R. B. & Branson, H. R., The structure of proteins: Two hydrogen-bonded helical configurations of the polypeptide chain. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* **37**, 205–211 (1951).
- [7] Dahiyat, B. I. & Mayo, S. L., De Novo Protein Design: Fully Automated Sequence Selection. *Science* **278**, 82–87 (1997).
- [8] Harbury, P. B., Plecs, J. J., Tidor, B., Alber, T. & Kim, P. S., High-Resolution Protein Design with Backbone Freedom. *Science* **282**, 1462–1467 (1998).
- [9] Kuhlman, B. *et al.*, Design of a Novel Globular Protein Fold with Atomic-Level Accuracy. *Science* **302**, 1364–1368 (2003).
- [10] Simons, K. T., Bonneau, R., Ruczynski, I. & Baker, D. Ab initio protein structure prediction of CASP III targets using ROSETTA. *Proteins: Struct., Funct., Bioinform.* **37**, 171–176 (1999).
- [11] Jones, T. A. & Thirup, S., Using known substructures in protein model building and crystallography. *EMBO J.* **5**, 819–822 (1986).
- [12] Huang, P.-S., Boyken, S. E. & Baker, D., The coming of age of de novo protein design. *Nature* **537**, 320–327 (2016).
- [13] Jiang, L. *et al.*, De Novo Computational Design of Retro-Aldol Enzymes. *Science* **319**, 1387–1391 (2008).
- [14] Röthlisberger, D. *et al.*, Kemp elimination catalysts by computational enzyme design. *Nature* **453**, 190–195 (2008).
- [15] Tinberg, C. E. *et al.*, Computational design of ligand-binding proteins with high affinity and selectivity. *Nature* **501**, 212–216 (2013).
- [16] Bale, J. B. *et al.*, Accurate design of megadalton-scale two-component icosahedral protein complexes. *Science* **353**, 389–394 (2016).
- [17] Langan, R. A. *et al.*, De Novo Design of Bioactive Protein Switches. *Nature* **572**, 205–210 (2019).
- [18] Bick, M. J. *et al.*, Computational design of environmental sensors for the potent opioid fentanyl. *eLife* **6**, e28909 (2017).
- [19] Moult, J., Pedersen, J. T., Judson, R. & Fidelis, K., A large-scale experiment to assess protein structure prediction methods. *Proteins: Struct., Funct., Bioinform.* **23**, ii–iv (1995).
- [20] Moult, J., Fidelis, K., Zemla, A. & Hubbard, T., Critical assessment of methods of protein structure prediction (CASP): Round IV. *Proteins: Struct., Funct., Genet.* **45**, 2–7 (2001).
- [21] Senior, A. W. *et al.*, Improved protein structure prediction using potentials from deep learning. *Nature* **577**, 706–710 (2020).
- [22] Silver, D. *et al.*, A general reinforcement learning algorithm that masters chess, shogi, and Go through self-play. *Science* **362**, 1140–1144 (2018).
- [23] Callaway, E., ‘It will change everything’: DeepMind’s AI makes gigantic leap in solving protein structures. *Nature* **588**, 203–204 (2020).
- [24] Jumper, J. *et al.*, Highly accurate protein structure prediction with AlphaFold. *Nature* **596**, 583–589 (2021).
- [25] Kryshchuk, A., Schwede, T., Topf, M., Fidelis, K. & Moult, J., Critical assessment of methods of protein structure prediction (CASP)—Round XIV. *Proteins: Struct., Funct., Bioinform.* **89**, 1607–1617 (2021).
- [26] Vaswani, A. *et al.*, Attention Is All You Need. *arXiv* (2017) doi:10.48550/arxiv.1706.03762.
- [27] Baek, M. *et al.*, Accurate prediction of protein structures and interactions using a three-track neural network. *Science* **373**, 871–876 (2021).
- [28] Wu, T., Stein, R. A., Kao, T.-Y., Brown, B. & Mchaourab, H. S., Modeling Protein Conformations by Guiding AlphaFold2 with Distance Distributions. Application to Double Electron Electron Resonance (DEER) Spectroscopy. *bioRxiv* 2024.10.30.621127 (2024) doi:10.1101/2024.10.30.621127.
- [29] Ahdriz, G. *et al.*, OpenFold: Retraining AlphaFold2 yields new insights into its learning mechanisms and capacity for generalization. (2022) doi:10.1101/2022.11.20.517210.
- [30] Bryant, P. & Noé, F., Structure prediction of alternative protein conformations. *Nat. Commun.* **15**, 7328 (2024).
- [31] Jing, B., Berger, B. & Jaakkola, T., AlphaFold Meets Flow Matching for Generating Protein Ensembles. *arXiv* (2024).
- [32] Mirdita, M. *et al.*, ColabFold: making protein folding accessible to all. *Nat Methods* **1–4** (2022) doi:10.1038/s41592-022-01488-1.
- [33] Abramson, J. *et al.*, Accurate structure prediction of biomolecular interactions with AlphaFold 3. *Nature* **1–3** (2024) doi:10.1038/s41586-024-07487-w.
- [34] Desai, D. *et al.*, Review of AlphaFold 3: Transformative Advances in Drug Design and Therapeutics. *Cureus* **16**, e63646 (2024).
- [35] Discovery, C. *et al.*, Chai-1: Decoding the molecular interactions of life. *bioRxiv* 2024.10.10.615955 (2024) doi:10.1101/2024.10.10.615955.
- [36] Wohlwend, J. *et al.*, Boltz-1: Democratizing Biomolecular Interaction Modeling. *bioRxiv* 2024.11.19.624167 (2024) doi:10.1101/2024.11.19.624167.
- [37] Willmott P., SLS 2.0 – The upgrade of the Swiss Light Source. *SPG Mitteilungen* **72**, 18–25 (2024).
- [38] Ruffolo, J. A., Chu, L.-S., Mahajan, S. P. & Gray, J. J., Fast, accurate antibody structure prediction from deep learning on massive set of natural antibodies. *Nat. Commun.* **14**, 2389 (2023).
- [39] Abanades, B. *et al.*, ImmuneBuilder: Deep-Learning models for predicting the structures of immune proteins. *Commun. Biol.* **6**, 575 (2023).
- [40] Lee, J. H. *et al.*, EquiFold: Protein Structure Prediction with a Novel Coarse-Grained Structure Representation. *bioRxiv* 2022.10.07.511322 (2023) doi:10.1101/2022.10.07.511322.
- [41] Ruffolo, J. A., Sulam, J. & Gray, J. J., Antibody structure prediction using interpretable deep learning. *Patterns* **3**, 100406 (2022).
- [42] Shانهsazzadeh, A. *et al.*, IgDesign: In vitro validated antibody design against multiple therapeutic antigens using inverse folding. *bioRxiv* 2023.12.08.570889 (2024) doi:10.1101/2023.12.08.570889.
- [43] Arnold, C., Inside the nascent industry of AI-designed drugs. *Nat. Med.* **29**, 1292–1295 (2023).
- [44] Chaves, E. J. F. *et al.*, Structure-based computational design of antibody mimetics: challenges and perspectives. *FEBS Open Bio* (2024) doi:10.1002/2211-5463.13855.
- [45] Huang, B. *et al.*, De novo design of miniprotein antagonists of cytokine storm inducers. *Nat. Commun.* **15**, 7064 (2024).
- [46] Varadi, M. *et al.*, AlphaFold Protein Structure Database: massively expanding the structural coverage of protein-sequence space with high-accuracy models. *Nucleic acids Res.* **50**, D439–D444 (2022).

Johan Åqvist obtained his PhD degree in Computational Structural Biology in 1987 from the Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences in Uppsala. He then spent two years as a postdoctoral researcher at the Department of Chemistry, University of Southern California. After returning to Sweden he was Assistant and Associate Professor of Structural Biology at Uppsala University during the period 1990-1999. He was then appointed Professor of Theoretical Chemistry at Uppsala University in 2000 and was also appointed Senior Researcher of the Swedish Research Council (2000-2006). He was elected to the Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences in 2009. Åqvist's research has dealt with computational studies of key biochemical problems such as enzyme catalysis, structure-based ligand design, ion channel permeation and protein synthesis by ribosomes. He is currently focusing on enzyme adaptation to extreme environments.

Hubert Kettenberger studied chemistry at the University of Regensburg and the University of Sussex/UK. He earned his PhD in structural biology from Ludwig Maximilians University Munich, working on the structure of RNA Polymerase II complexes. Following his doctoral studies, he completed a postdoctoral fellowship in cryo-electron microscopy at the Max Planck Institute for Biochemistry in Martinsried. He subsequently joined the Roche research site in Penzberg.

In various roles as a scientist and group leader, he developed a longstanding research interest in understanding and predicting the structures and biophysical properties of therapeutic proteins, such as stability, pharmacokinetics, and solubility, which are collectively referred to as “developability.” Since its inception in 2018, Hubert Kettenberger has been leading the department for computational protein engineering. With the advent of powerful computational methods, this research group focuses on the development and application of in-silico methods to the drug design process.